

RNA extraction and purification

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Protocol description

RNA extraction and sequencing.

Materials

Biological materials:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ WT-OE, KO or KO-OE RESOLUTE cell lines▪ DNaseI (Sigma-Aldrich, 4716728001)
Reagents:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ RDD buffer (Qiagen, 1011132)▪ RNeasy 96 RNA purification kit (Qiagen, 74182)
Equipment:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ QIAvac 96 Vacuum system (Qiagen, 19504)▪ Centrifuge with rotor for 96-well plates suitable for 6000 rpm (~5600 x g)

Reagents setup

DNaseI solution

Add 360 µl DNaseI to 1640 µl RNA-free H₂O and 14 ml RDD buffer.

Procedure

▪ Harvesting Cells

1. In a 12 well plate, seed 0.25×10^6 cells in 4 wells (if the cell line is K.O., seed 2 wells only).
2. Induce at the same time 2 wells with doxycycline. Incubate cells for at least 24 hours.
3. Harvest cells by completely removing medium by aspiration and then add 205 µl of Buffer RLT to each well of the microplate.
4. Keeping the microplate flat on the bench, shake it vigorously back and forth for 10 s. While continuing to keep the plate flat on the bench, rotate the plate by 90° and shake it for an additional 10 s.
5. Collect 200 ul of lysate (do not scrape it, just gently resuspend the lysate) into safe-lock tubes and freeze at -80°C.

▪ RNA Purification

1. Thaw lysates on ice at least 2 hours before purification
2. Prepare DNaseI
3. Prepare RPE buffer in advance if necessary
4. Assemble QIAvac 96 vacuum manifold in the pump.
5. Keep samples on ice while you remove lids of both plates.

6. Add 1 volume (200 μ L) of 70% ethanol if you had collected 200 μ L of lysate. Mix by pipetting up and down 5 times. Apply the samples (400 μ L) into the wells of the RNeasy 96 plate. Do it only on one plate.
7. Switch on vacuum source. Apply vacuum until transfer is complete. In the meanwhile, start doing step 4 to the second plate. Switch off vacuum and ventilate QIAvac 96 manifold. Make sure QIAvac 96 vacuum manifold is assembled correctly before loading. The flow-through is collected in the waste tray.
8. Pipet 80 μ L of the DNase I incubation mix directly onto the RNeasy membrane in each well of the RNeasy 96 plate. Seal the plate with an AirPore Tape Sheet. Make sure to pipet the DNase I incubation mix directly onto the RNeasy membrane. Place at room temperature for 15 min.
9. Add 1 mL of Buffer RW1 to each well of the RNeasy 96 plate and wait 5 min before proceeding. Seal the plate with an AirPore Tape Sheet and place it on top of a Square-Well Block. Centrifuge at 6000 rpm (\sim 5600 x g) for 4 min at room temperature.
10. Add 1 mL of Buffer RPE to each well of the RNeasy 96 plate. Centrifuge at 6000 rpm (\sim 5600 x g) for 4 min at room temperature.
11. Add another 1 mL of Buffer RPE to each well of the RNeasy 96 plate. Centrifuge at 6000 rpm (\sim 5600 x g) for 10 min at room temperature to dry the plate membranes.
12. Place RNeasy 96 plate on top of an elution microtube rack containing 1.2 mL elution microtubes labelled with your RNA plate number
13. To elute the RNA, add 60 μ L of RNase-free water to each well, and seal the RNeasy 96 plate with a new sheet of AirPore Tape. Incubate for 1 min at room temperature. Then centrifuge at 6000 rpm (\sim 5600 x g) for 4 min at room temperature. Make sure to pipet the RNase-free water directly onto the RNeasy membrane.
14. Use caps provided to seal the microtubes for storage. Store RNA at -80°C .

Additional notes

Data availability

<https://re-solute.eu/resources/dashboards/transcriptomics/analysis/>

<https://re-solute.eu/resources/datasets>

References

Please write to contact@re-solute.eu in case of questions or errors.